

THE ROLE OF SAFETY CULTURE AND SAFETY BEHAVIOR IN MEDIATING THE INFLUENCE OF SAFETY LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOR ON SAFETY PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

The general objective of the research is to develop a new model of the determinants of safety performance based on the concepts of safety management and leadership follower theory. Partially least square (PLS-SEM) is used in this study. Total sampling was used to obtain a sample size of 102 participants, which was obtained using an online questionnaire. Exogenous variables (safety leadership behavior), endogenous variables (safety performance), and certain moderating roles were used in this study. Safety leadership behavior has a significant positive effect on safety culture directly. However, the direct effect of safety leadership behavior on safety behavior and safety performance is not significant. The safety culture variable has a positive and significant effect on safety behavior in a direct relationship, but its effect on safety performance is not significant. The safety behavior variable has a positive and significant effect on safety performance. This study succeeded in revealing the existence of safety culture and safety behavior variables as mediator variables. The existence of safety leadership behavior is not able to provide a direct influence on safety behavior but requires a safety culture that plays a role as a full mediator of the influence of safety leadership behavior on safety behavior.

Keywords: Safety leadership behavior, safety performance, safety culture, safety behavior, mediator

INTRODUCTION

Upstream oil and gas operations are activities that are high in risk, cost, and technology. Activities in this sector must always be monitored and fostered so as not to cause large losses, both losses to workers, the general public, assets, or the environment. Various codes and standards and regulations have been issued regarding this activity to achieve safe upstream oil and gas operations without accidents. Safety is the main factor that must inspire upstream oil and gas operations (Dirjen Migas, 2021). Based on the circular letter of the Director of Oil and Gas Mining Engineering as Head of Oil and Gas Mining Inspection dated October 25, 1996, there are four classifications of mining accidents, namely minor, moderate, heavy, and fatal. Minor accidents in 2021 occurred 80 times. Moderate accidents in 2021 occurred as many as 9 accidents, a decrease of 12 cases from the previous year. In 2021, the number of heavy labor accidents in the oil and gas industries has decreased compared to 2020, from 7 accidents to 3 serious accidents in the oil and gas industry. The incidence of fatal accidents in the Oil and Gas industry in 2021 was 6 accidents, an increase of 1 case compared to 2020 (Dirjen Migas, 2022).

Safety performance still needs to be improved. The target of work safety is zero accidents, i.e. the work accident rate is zero (0) so that the workplace becomes a safe place for workers. As long as this zero (0) value has not been achieved, efforts to improve safety performance must still be increased. Safety management practices enable organizations to lessen the possibility of accidents, injuries, and near misses the organization's actual role is to practice safety management to stay safe. Therefore, it is understandable that ensuring workplace health and safety remains the greatest challenge for practitioners and theorists alike (Ajmal et al., 2021). Several studies have shown that the existence of company leaders is very important for companies to achieve a high level of performance, such as research conducted by Basit et al. (2017), Haq&Kuchinke (2016), and Peterson et al. (2003). In the context of leadership behavior and safety performance, there are still inconsistencies. Research by Yang et al. (2010) showed that leadership behavior has a direct effect on safety performance, meanwhile, Makaske's (2015) research shows that leadership behavior does not have a significant effect on team effectiveness, and according to Skeepers&Mbohwa's (2015) research, leadership conduct has no direct effect on safety performance. The findings above imply that there is currently a study deficit in the area of leadership behavior and safety performance. The existence of this research gap represents an opportunity for a study to be conducted.

Several studies have indicated that the human factor has a significant role in the occurrence of work accidents, accounting for 80-85 percent of the time (Pratama, 2015). A worker who performs an unsafe action has a background as to why they perform an unsafe act. Human safety behavior is a reflection of various psychological conditions such as knowledge, desire, interest, emotion, will, thinking, motivation, perception, attitude, reaction, and so on (Abidin et al., 2008). Culture can also play an important role in creating a performance. A strong culture can often improve corporate success by instilling a high degree of motivation in personnel. It is sometimes highlighted that common beliefs and behaviors help workers feel at ease working for the organization and that a sense of commitment or loyalty motivates people to work harder. Certain practices that are thought to be frequent in firms with strong cultures are sometimes considered to make work inherently rewarding. Two common examples include including individuals in decision-making and recognizing their contributions. Sometimes a strong culture is said by Mukesh dan Lingadurai (2014) can help improve company performance.

Based on the background description that has been presented, can be conveyed the formulation of the general problem in this study, what variables are the determinants of safety performance based on the concept of safety management and leadership follower theory?

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Literature Review

Since the beginning of industrial operations, many dangers have arisen for humans, the environment, and the business itself. Various efforts have been undertaken to reduce these hazards to conduct industrial operations safely. The lack of a proper safety management system has been the fundamental cause of most industrial tragedies in the past. Safety management methods not only enhance working conditions but also have a favorable impact on employee

safety attitudes and behavior, resulting in fewer workplace incidents (Ahammad, 2015). Organizations can reduce the likelihood of accidents, injuries, and near misses by using safety management measures. The role of safety management in a business is to keep everyone safe. As a result, it's natural that safeguarding workplace health and safety continues to be the most difficult task for both practitioners and theorists (Ajmal et al., 2021). Companies must pay attention to occupational safety and health management as a concern for aspects such as production, sales, transportation, and quality control (OSHAcademy, 2021).

There are various definitions of safety management, such as arrangements made by an organization for safety management to cultivate a strong safety culture and achieve high safety performance a methodical approach to safety management that incorporates the necessary organizational structures, responsibility, policies, and procedures. Safety is concerned with discovering operational flaws and developing control systems to prevent them from occurring again (Ahammad, 2015). The old saying, "Safety First" should not just be jargon, but safety is more effective if it is considered a priority in a highly competitive environment, priorities can change quickly. To survive, companies must produce and be safe. The phrase "Safety First" should be "Safety only". "Safety Only" emphasizes one idea that it's okay to produce as hard and fast as you can if you can do it safely. High productivity is desirable, but if a hazard or safety practice is discovered that could cause serious physical injury or death, it must be corrected immediately, even if it means stopping production. This condition is called a commitment to safety (OSHAcademy, 2021).

One of the basic premises of safety management is that management should be responsible for safety. This premise can be traced back to the classics, but it is still prevalent in most safety management texts. For example, the essential concepts of safety management are all related to the construction of a management system that aims to control the operational performance of the business (Ahammad, 2015).

The concept of safety performance is very important to be applied to industry, especially in the Oil and Gas Industry. Culture is one of the factors that play an important role in creating a safe performance (Mukesh & Lingadurai, 2014). Safety culture is a component of OHS attitudes, ideas, and values in an organization. Safety culture is a mindset that emphasizes the importance of safety in businesses and individuals. All responsibilities relating to safety must be carried out accurately, thoughtfully, and with a strong sense of responsibility, in a safety culture (Abidin et al., 2008). Safe behavior at work will ultimately be able to create an effective Workplace health and safety Management System and can reduce the number of work accidents that occur within the company or have a good safety performance (Çakıt et al., 2019). Safety behavior is also an important aspect of creating safety performance. Hsiang (2011) has investigated the relationship between safety culture, safety behavior, and safety performance, and explained the causal factors that influence the three dimensions above. Safety leadership can also effectively contribute to organizational safety (Tao et al., 2020). Various literature suggests that leadership is one of the most important factors in guaranteeing safety (Schopf et al., 2021).

Hypotheses development

Managers who support safety have been identified as an essential component of a safety culture. Zohar (2002) has established that managers and leaders who promote safety initiatives offer both direct and indirect advantages in terms of organizational culture. According to Lee (2002) manager leadership behavior, organizational culture, and organizational vision are all key components in effective organizational management. Zohar (2002) shows that a leader who encourages employees' motivation to develop a safety culture can be increased through worker participation and system implementation. Based on these conditions, the hypotheses that can be proposed are:

H₁: Safety leadership behavior has a positive and significant effect on the safety culture of employees of the oil and gas industry in East Borneo.

Effective safety leadership is financially beneficial for company performance (Veltri et al., 2007). These conditions have a favorable impact on employee safety behaviors and attitudes and lead to reduce accident rates and insurance premiums while increasing efficiency by eliminating production bottlenecks. Safety and operational excellence are inextricably linked. Companies that excel at controlling workplace safety are also adept at managing operations (Muñiz et al., 2009). Leaders are expected to be able to inspire an organization. Leaders should be excited and enthusiastic to convey their goals and invite the people they lead to achieve these goals. Inspirational leaders sincerely believe in salvation, and this is shown in their body language, tone, words said, and daily activities. They also construct a vision that paints a positive picture of the future while selling its benefits (Cooper, 2015). Leaders have behaviors that describe the vision and mission to be achieved.

When it comes to workplace safety, inspirational leaders also invite people to join them and get involved in achieving an articulated vision. Inspirational leaders know how to strengthen the optimism and enthusiasm of those around them to achieve better results. In some circumstances, such leaders assist in the development of people's knowledge, skills, and talents so that they may more completely participate in safety efforts by showing safe behaviors that are required by corporate standards (Serrat, 2021). Various leadership characteristics can affect the efficacy of safety performance. Clarke & Ward (2006) demonstrate that leadership style has a substantial impact on the link with safety involvement, and leaders can support safety participation by employing a variety of influence strategies. Leaders are critical in high-reliability organizations. Wu et al. (2008) have conducted a statistical analysis that demonstrated that organizational leaders would benefit from developing methods to improve the safety climate within their firms, which would then have a strong beneficial effect on safety performance. Based on these conditions, the hypotheses that can be proposed are:

H₂: Safety leadership behavior has a positive and significant effect on the safety behavior of employees of the oil and gas industry in East Borneo.

According to Posner & Schmidt (2004), the most important value of a leader is his personality with this personality the leader can influence the choices made by his subordinates, influence the things they believe in, influence their interests, and influence the way subordinates to invest

their time and energy. Skeepers & Mbohwa (2015) argue that for continuous improvement and improvement of safety performance, company management must be consistent with the plan-do-check-act cycle. The management committee of employees must also be involved in the cycle. Planning, implementation, and operation are all part of the cycle, as are proactive and reactive checking, corrective action, and management review. Tandoh's research (2011) shows that leadership conduct has a favorable and significant effect on staff performance. Employee performance cannot be divorced from the leader's responsibility of providing instructions and caring for employees, as well as always setting goals and criteria that must be met by employees in carrying out their jobs, to establish harmonious working conditions. That way, employees will feel motivated by the presence of pleasant working conditions. Thus, employees feel comfortable with the conditions of the services provided and they will be motivated to improve their performance. The hypotheses that can be proposed are:

H₃: Safety leadership behavior has a positive and significant effect on the safety performance of employees of the oil and gas industry in East Borneo.

Helmreich & Merritt (2000) created a model of the factors that can lead to a safety culture and safety behavior. This model can also influence the manner and type of training delivery. Professional culture can influence safety culture through sentiments of responsibility. Muñiz et al. (2009) define the phrase safety culture, as well as a theoretical model for how safety culture works and drives organizational safety behavior. Darby & Wilson (2005) also identified forty major influences on safe behavior and safety culture. Hsiang (2011) classifies unsafe behavior into six broad categories: the use of inappropriate tools, inappropriate work strategies that endanger oneself, failure to use personal protection equipment, incorrect tool storage, wrong storage by others, and unsafe work techniques endangering others. Accidents in the workplace might occur as a result of risky activity. One way that can be used to reduce the occurrence of accidents in the workplace is the existence of a safety culture. Safety culture can be formed by the presence of factors forming a safety culture (Suyono & Nawawinetu, 2013). Likewise with the social environment, the better the social environment of the workers, the better the behavior of workers towards OHS (Suyono & Nawawinetu, 2013). Based on these conditions, the hypotheses that can be proposed are:

H₄: Safety culture has a positive and significant effect on the safety behavior of employees of the oil and gas industry in East Borneo.

Good working conditions and safe work is a requirement to achieve a supportive work environment for workers, especially in construction projects. This needs attention because the project work location is one of the work environments that contain a large enough risk, As a result, the construction industry is regarded as the most vulnerable to workplace accidents. Lack of incentive to develop a safety culture at the organizational and project levels has resulted in a poor overall safety record, with construction being one of the most dangerous industries in the world (Hsiang, 2011). Cooper (2015) proposed a reciprocal safety culture model to comprehend its dynamism, multifaceted, and comprehensive nature. The promotion of a positive safety culture is currently seen as a realistic risk management strategy, to develop a culture within the business in which everyone is personally active in maintaining safety

(Hudson, 2009). Cullen (2016) has recommended high-risk businesses refocus their attention away from accident and incident numbers and toward examining the cultures and climates that may contribute to occurrences. According to O'Toole (2002), safety culture is an important aspect that establishes the value of safety in a business.

Occupational safety and health programs should start from the most basic stage, namely the establishment of a culture of occupational safety and health (Reason, 2007). There is an interesting phenomenon that is owned by the oil and gas industry, namely first that the oil and gas industry services is an industry that has a large enough risk, but can be reduced by the existence of a workplace health and safety program through the formation of work culture, one of which is a culture of occupational safety and health. Second, the oil and gas industry is an industry that is not only oriented to finished products as in other industries but is process-oriented. Based on these conditions, the hypotheses that can be proposed are:

H₅: Safety culture has a positive and significant effect on the safety performance of employees of the oil and gas industry in East Borneo.

According to Dessler (2015), the main causes of accidents are unsafe conditions and unsafe behavior. An unsafe condition is a condition that physically or mechanically can cause an accident. This includes unsafe conditions such as equipment that is not properly secured, damaged equipment, and dangerous company/organization procedures. Unsafe behavior is an unsafe act caused by human negligence itself, such as not using personal protective equipment procedures at work, throwing objects carelessly, and using unsafe equipment. In domino theory, 88% of work accidents are caused by unsafe behavior (unsafe behavior) from employees who do the work (Khosravi et al., 2014). In addition, unsafe behavior is also caused by the lack of provision of employees for work safety and the lack of understanding and application of employees on work safety procedures, such as personal protective equipment (Pangihutan, 2019). Conversely, when employees have good safety behavior, the rate of work accidents will decrease.

Organizational structure improvements, the importance of safety, safety responsibility and accountability, communication, management behavior, employee engagement, and employee response and behavior can all contribute to improving safety performance (Erickson, 2015). According to Vredenburg (2012), safety behavior is frequently connected with performance quality. As a result, the co-benefits of safe behavior may enhance productivity. According to Garavan & O'Brien (2011), dangerous activities or behaviors were the leading cause of workplace accidents or injuries. Based on these conditions, the hypotheses that can be proposed are:

H₆: Safety behavior has a positive and significant effect on the safety performance of oil and gas industry employees in East Borneo.

Leaders determine organizational culture. This is because, from the responses of subordinates, the leader identifies which policies, procedures, practices, and behaviors will be rewarded or supported (Shen et al., 2015). In the end, this formed culture can create a good performance. In the study of safety performance, the right culture is to be studied by safety culture. According

to Lee (2002) manager leadership behavior, organizational culture, and organizational vision are all critical components of successful organizational management. Zohar (2002) shows that a leader who encourages worker participation and system implementation can increase employees' desire to improve the safety culture. Based on these conditions, the hypotheses that can be proposed are:

H7: Safety culture and safety behavior as mediators of the influence of safety leadership behavior on the safety performance of oil and gas industry employees in East Borneo.

Figure 1: Empirical Research Model

The following Figure 1 depicts the empirical research model that shows the relationships between safety leadership behavior, safety culture, safety behavior, and safety performance well-being about the hypothesis.

METHODS

This quantitative study looks into the function of safety culture and safety behavior in mitigating the impact of safety leadership behavior on safety performance. This study's population consisted of all employees who worked in the OHS unit at 5 (five) oil and gas companies in East Borneo, namely Badak Natural Gas Pertamina RU-V, Vico, Unocal, and Total. The research topic is about safety performance and employees who know are employees of the OHS section. The number of employees working in the OHS section of five oil and gas companies in East Borneo is 102 employees. So the total population in this study was 102 employees.

There are three types of variables studied in this study, namely exogenous variables, endogenous variables, and mediator variables. Exogenous variables are independent variables that have an impact on the dependent variable Exogenous variables are represented in the SEM model by the existence of arrows leading from these variables to endogenous variables (Santoso, 2011). The exogenous variable in this study is safety leadership behavior. Next are endogenous variables. Endogenous variables are dependent variables that are independent

factors that influence or are exogenous. Endogenous variables are highlighted in the SEM model by the existence of arrows leading to them (Santoso, 2011). The endogenous variable in this study is safety performance. The last is the mediator or intervening variable, namely the variable that mediates or mediates the effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables (Santoso, 2011). Variables that fall into the category of mediator or intervening are safety culture and safety behavior variables.

The data collection method used is by using a questionnaire. The questionnaire is an investigation of something that concerns the public interest (the crowd) and is carried out by circulating a statement list form, submitted in writing to several objects to get a written answer or response (response). The questionnaire was prepared based on operational definitions that have been carried out to explain each variable in the study. The indicators for the four variables are manifested in the form of statements in the questionnaire with a Five Point Likert Scale (1 = strongly disagree 2 = Disagree 3 = Neutral 4 = Agree 5 = strongly agree).

The analytical techniques used include descriptive and inferential analysis. Descriptive statistics are used to describe the identity of respondents and respondents' answers to statements related to the variables studied. The identity of the respondents in the form of gender, age, education, name of the company where they work, position in the company, and length of service in the company, is presented in the identity table, both absolute and relative numbers.

The stages in the PLS analysis is as follows: Constructing the Model, Outer Model Evaluation, Inner Model Evaluation, and Hypothesis Testing.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result

This research was conducted in East Borneo involving 5 (five) changes to oil and gas. The five companies are: Badak NGL, Pertamina RU-V, Pertamina Hulu Sanga-Sanga, Pertamina Hulu East Borneo, and Pertamina Hulu Mahakam. The selected respondents came from the five companies totaling 102 people. All respondents are employees of the OHS section of the selected oil and Gas Company. The selection of research respondents used saturated sampling, which is a sampling technique in which all members of the population are used as samples in the study (Ansori, 2020: 113). The number of respondents selected in this study amounted to 102 people.

Profile		Frequency	
		N	%
Gender	Female	96	94,1
	Male	6	5,9
Age	20 – 29 years	12	11,8
	30 – 39 years	32	31,4
	40 – 49 years	40	39,2
	50 – 59 years	18	17,6
Education	Diploma	23	22,5
	Postgraduate	15	14,7
	Bachelor	50	49,0
	Senior High School	14	13,7
Position	Assistant manager	5	4,9
	HSE Officer	82	80,4
	Supervisor	15	14,7
Work experience	0 - 5 years	17	16,7
	6 - 10 years	23	22,5
	11 - 15 years	22	21,6
	16 - 20 years	10	9,8
	> 20 years	30	29,4

Table 1 shows a description of the respondents involved in this research. The majority of research respondents were male, which amounted to 96 people or equivalent to 94.1% of the total number of research respondents. Most respondents are aged between 40 – and 49 years with a total of 40 people or 39.2% of the total research respondents. The majority of respondents are respondents of adult age, more than 30 years. Respondents with undergraduate education level had the most number, reaching 50 people or equivalent to 49.0% of the total research respondents. The majority of research respondents were OHS staff with a total of 82 respondents or 80.4% of all research respondents.

The PLS model was made twice. In the first model, there are two invalid statements, namely the second statement from the safety behavior variable (sb2) and the first statement from the safety performance variable (sp1). The results of the second running model, after sb2 and sp1 were removed from the model, can be seen in the model below.

Figure 20: Full Test of Research Model

Figure 2 presents the results of the research model test that presents the coefficient value of each statement on the latent variable and the path coefficient value on each relationship between the latent variables studied. The next step is to test whether the coefficient value generated in the model test has met the requirements or not.

Based on the findings of the path coefficient test of the research model, it is found that 6 paths have positive values, so it is possible to deduce that all paths have a positive effect on safety performance. The stages of testing carried out on the outer model are as follows: 1) Convergent validity. It is said that a condition is valid if the loading factor on the latent variable with its statements > 0.5 ; 2) Discriminant validity. The way to measure is by comparing the loading value on the intended construct with other constructs and it must be greater; 3) Composite reliability. It is said that a condition is reliable if composite reliability greater than 0.8 already has high reliability; 4) Cronbach alpha. The reliability test was strengthened by Cronbach Alpha. The accepted value is greater than 0.6 for all constructs.

Testing all research indicators, it can be seen that all indicators meet the conditions of convergent validity and discriminant validity. Meanwhile, for research variables, all research variables meet the requirements in composite reliability and Cronbach alpha.

Hypothesis testing is done by looking at the path coefficient and t value. Path coefficients (estimates for path coefficients) in smart PLS 2 are obtained by bootstrapping path coefficient procedures (Original Sample column), statistical t-test (t statistics column), and significant test (p-value column). There are 6 lines tested. Table 2 presents data for hypothesis testing which includes the direction of the variable relationship, t value, significance, and decision on the hypothesis.

Table 2: Results of hypothesis testing

Hypothesis	Influence	Coefficient	relationship direction	Significance	Conclusion
H ₁	SLB -> SC	0,935	Positive	0,000 Significance<0,05	Significant
H ₂	SLB -> SB	0,111	Positive	0,665 Significance>0,05	Not significant
H ₃	SLB -> SP	0,355	Positive	0,148 Significance>0,05	Not significant
H ₄	SC -> SB	0,786	Positive	0,000 Significance<0,05	Significant
H ₅	SC -> SP	0,245	Positive	0,356 Significance>0,05	Not significant
H ₆	SB -> SP	0,277	Positive	0,038 Significance<0,05	Significant

The data shows that of the six hypotheses that have been proposed, three hypotheses are proven, to have a positive and significant effect. Meanwhile, the other three hypotheses are not significant.

Table 3 shows that the mediation formed are full mediation.

Table 3: Indirect Effect

Relation	Indirect	Coefficient	Significance	Conclusion	Information
SLB -> SB	SLB → SC → SB	0,847	0,000 Significance <0,05	Significant	Full Mediation
SC -> SP	SC → SB → SP	0,463	0,030 Significance <0,05	Significant	Full Mediation
SLB -> SP	SLB → SC → SB → SP	0,818	0,000 Significance <0,05	Significant	Full Mediation

The explanations of the three fully formed mediations are as follows: 1) SLB – SB. On the SLB to SB path, there are direct and indirect paths. In the direct path, the effect of SLB SB is not significant (sig value = 0.665 > 0.05). Meanwhile, the indirect effect (SLB SC SB) was significant (sig=0.000 <0.05). Therefore, SC becomes a mediator of the influence of SLB on SB. The model formed is full mediation. 2) SC – SP. On the SC to SP path, there is a direct path and an indirect path. In the direct path, the effect of SC SP was not significant (sig value = 0.356 > 0.05). Meanwhile, the indirect effect (SC SB SP) was significant (sig=0.000 <0.05). Therefore, the SB becomes a mediator of the influence of the SC on the SP. The model formed is full mediation; 3) SLB – SP. On the SLB to SP path, there are direct and indirect paths. In the direct path, the effect of SLB SP was not significant (sig value = 0.148 > 0.05). Meanwhile,

the indirect effect (SLB SC SB SP) was significant ($\text{sig}=0.000 < 0.05$). Therefore, SC and SB become mediators of the influence of SLB on SP. The model formed is full mediation.

Discussion

Safety Leadership Behavior Has Positive and Significant Influence on Safety Culture of Oil and Gas Industry Employees in East Borneo

The results of testing on research data discovered that safety leadership behavior has a strong and positive impact on safety culture, so the hypothesis to safety leadership behavior has a significant effect on safety culture is proven. The leadership, in this case, the OHS manager as the highest leader in the OHS division, must be able to demonstrate leadership behavior in terms of workplace health and safety this can be accomplished through defining a compelling vision for the future, encouraging team members to think for themselves, and participating in employee safety activities.

Leadership behavior in the aspect of work safety will be able to influence the attitudes and safety culture of the employees who are under their control. A leader who provides support for workplace health and safety management is recognized as a basic element in forming a safety culture in the company. As mentioned by Zohar (2002) that leaders who support workplace health and safety management have a direct or indirect impact on the formation of culture within the company. A leader who encourages worker participation and system implementation can increase employees' desire to improve safety culture (Zohar, 2002).

This research uses the concept of safety management relationship as the main theory used. In this concept, the leadership aspect plays an important role. Two behavioral components that stand out in the oil and gas industry in East Borneo are the leadership providing information related to the implementation of safety in the company and the leadership ensuring that all employees understand the safety principles in the company. These two aspects are considered by OHS employees in East Borneo as the most prominent aspects of their leaders. The activeness of the leadership to provide information related to OHS and the leadership who continues to ensure that employees understand the OHS principles that exist in the company can finally form a good OHS culture in oil and gas companies in East Borneo.

Safety Leadership Behavior Has No Significant Effect on Safety Behavior of Oil and Gas Industry Employees in East Borneo

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workplace health and safety management is recognized as a basic element in forming a safety culture in the company. As mentioned by Zohar (2002) that leaders who support workplace health and safety management have a direct or indirect impact on the establishment of organizational culture. Employees' willingness to develop a safety culture can be increased by a leader who supports worker participation and system adoption (Zohar, 2002).

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Safety Leadership Behavior Has No Significant Effect on the Safety Performance of Oil and Gas Industry Employees in East Borneo

Safety leadership behavior has no significant effect on safety performance, so the third hypothesis which states that safety leadership behavior has a significant positive effect on safety performance is not proven. Safety performance is the level of workplace safety and health that can be achieved by the company through employees in the OHS division. This safety performance can be formed from the collaboration of all elements in the company, especially employees who work in the OHS section. Safety performance is indicated by eight indicators with the lowest value being "Help for coworkers", employees help their coworkers when they work in risky conditions, with a mean value of 4.657. Meanwhile, the indicator that has the largest mean value is "Use correct safety procedure", employees use correct safety procedures to do their work with a mean value of 6.519.

Meanwhile, safety leadership behavior refers more to the individual behavior of a leader to prioritize setting an example by the leader to his followers. A leader can change the behavior of his followers by making changes to his behavior. This leader's behavior will be an example for his followers so that followers will follow the behavior shown by their leaders (Wrench & Carter, 2012). Safety leadership behavior refers to the individual behavior of the leader, meanwhile, safety performance refers to the performance of all company employees.

The available data shows that the number of OHS employees in the five companies that were used as research respondents was 102 people, consisting of 5 assistant managers, 15 supervisors, and 82 OHS staff. The number of leaders who are assessed on the aspect of safety leadership behavior is 5 people, namely the OHS division manager. Personal contact made by the leader with his safety leadership behavior has not been able to have a significant effect on all employees so it has not been able to have a significant impact on employee safety performance. This condition is caused by the intensity of personal contact made by the OHS manager with the employees of the OHS section so that the influence given by the leadership's

work safety behavior does not directly affect the safety performance of the employees. The number of managers who only 5 people are not enough to make close personal contacts that can affect the performance of subordinates.

Safety Culture Has Positive and Significant Influence on Safety Behavior of Oil and Gas Industry Employees in East Borneo

As a result of the fourth hypothesis, safety culture has a positive and significant effect on safety behavior. Muñiz et al. (2009) define the term safety culture and present a theoretical model for how safety culture drives organizational safety behavior. Helmreich & Merritt (2000) created a model of the elements that can result in a safety culture and safety behavior. This model can also influence the style and content of training; professional culture can influence safety culture via feelings of responsibility.

Darby & Wilson (2005) identified forty major elements that determine safe behavior and culture. Hazardous conditions or emergency conditions in the workplace can be caused by unsafe behavior; therefore unsafe behavior must be eliminated. Every employee must have good safety behavior so that dangerous incidents or work accidents in the company can be suppressed. Creating a safety culture is one way that can be taken to shape work safety behavior in employees.

Three components of safety culture that stand out that ultimately have an impact on the creation of good work safety behavior are work processes, identification and risk management, and continuous improvement. Work processes are indicated by work processes carried out in a way that maintains work safety and environmental management; hazard identification and risk management are indicated by the identification of hazards and risk management are carried out fully and immediately handled or repaired commensurate with the impact that can be caused, and continuous improvement is indicated by continuous improvements made to ensure safety and environmental management are implemented. These three aspects are aspects that stand out in safety culture which ultimately have an impact on safety behavior.

Safety Culture Has No Significant Effect on Safety Performance of Oil and Gas Industry Employees in East Borneo

Safety culture has no positive and significant effect on safety performance, so the fifth hypothesis which states that safety culture has a significant positive effect on safety performance is not proven. Safety culture, which is the core value of all employees of the OHS division reflects a dedication to conducting business in a manner that protects people and the environment, as well as articulating the qualities or features of strong safety culture (Commite, 2016).

The culture adopted by an employee, apart from being influenced by the company's internal conditions, is also influenced by the internal individual concerned. Identification of the background of the respondent's area of origin shows that the area of origin of employees in the Oil and Gas industry varies, evenly in all regions in Indonesia. Most of the employees from Java, which is about 30%, from Sumatra and Borneo are relatively the same, which is about

20%. Approximately 12% of employees come from Sulawesi, around 14% of employees from Bali-Nusra, and around 4% of employees from Maluku-Papua. This variation in the area of origin of employees is also a factor in shaping the company's safety culture. The previous cultural background will play a role in the formation of a work safety culture within each worker.

Every activity in the Oil and Gas industry, especially those related to workplace health and safety, is made in writing, such as the Safety Culture. There are several provisions in the implementation of this program, such as "I CARE Leader", "Supervisor" and "Front Liner" Workshops, I CARE Communication, HSE Initiatives from the Division, Safety Feedback, Environmental Protection Program, and Health Program. The safety culture in the company has been formed in a formal regulation so that some OHS employees carry out work safety culture as a formality. This can also be seen from the questionnaire data recap, it can be seen that the "Inquiring attitude" indicator, namely "employees always question work practices as part of the daily conversation without hesitation to create workplace health and safety" has the lowest mean value compared to the indicator another. The criticality of employees on the conditions of Workplace health and safety in the company is still lacking. This fact is caused because the organization applies very procedural principles of culture. This condition ultimately resulted in safety culture not having a significant influence on safety performance.

Safety Behavior Has a Positive and Significant Effect on the Safety Performance of Oil and Gas Industry Employees in East Borneo

Because safety behavior has a positive and considerable impact on safety performance, the sixth hypothesis, safety behavior has a significant impact on safety performance, is supported. The main causes of accidents are unsafe conditions and unsafe actions or unsafe behavior (Dessler, 2015). In the domino theory, 88% of work accidents are caused by unsafe behavior from employees who do the work. In addition, unsafe behavior is also caused by the lack of provision of employees for work safety and the lack of understanding and application of employees on work safety procedures, such as personal protective equipment (Pangihutan, 2019). Conversely, when employees have good safety behavior, the rate of work accidents will decrease.

As a result, efforts to foster appropriate employee workplace conduct must continue. Organizational structure improvements, The significance of safety, safety responsibility and accountability, communication, management behavior, employee involvement, and employee response and behavior can all be emphasized to contribute to improving safety performance (Erickson, 2015).

Safety Culture and Safety Behavior as Mediators of the Effect of Safety Leadership Behavior on Safety Performance

According to the findings of this study, safety culture and safety behavior are mediators of the influence of safety leadership behavior on safety performance. This is because, from the responses of subordinates, the leader identifies which policies, procedures, practices, and

behaviors will be rewarded or supported (Shen et al., 2015). In the end, this formed culture can create a good performance.

In the study of safety performance, the right culture is to be studied by safety culture. According to Lee (2002) organizational culture, manager leadership behavior, and organizational vision are all key components in effective organizational management. According to Zohar (2002), a leader who promotes employee participation and system implementation can raise employees' willingness to improve the safety culture. Employee safety behavior was also influenced by the safety culture that was established.

This shows that a leader who encourages worker participation and system implementation can increase employees' desire to improve the safety culture. The safety culture that was formed also helped shape the safety behavior of employees.

CONCLUSION

This study raises a new concept, namely safety leadership behavior, which is a leadership behavior in the field of workplace health and safety in an industry that has a high work risk. In the proposed research model, there is one exogenous variable (safety leadership behavior), one endogenous variable (safety performance), and a mediator variable (safety culture, and safety behavior). The results show that safety leadership behavior has a significant positive effect on safety culture directly. However, the direct effect of safety leadership behavior on safety behavior and safety performance is not significant. The safety culture variable has a positive and significant effect on safety behavior in a direct relationship, but its effect on safety performance is not significant. The safety behavior variable has a positive and significant effect on safety performance. This study succeeded in revealing the existence of safety culture and safety behavior variables as mediator variables.

The implications based on these results can be explained that the existence of safety leadership behavior is not able to provide a direct influence on safety behavior, but requires a safety culture that plays a role as a full mediator of the influence of safety leadership behavior on safety behavior. The existence of a safety culture is not able to provide a direct influence on safety performance but requires safety behavior that plays a role as a full mediator of the influence of safety culture on safety performance. This understanding of safety leadership behavior is expected to provide a comprehensive understanding of the importance of the role of leadership behavior in creating a performance in the field of workplace health and safety.

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